

Effects of Orange - Fleshed Sweet Potato (OFSP) - Meal on the Growth and Carcass Weight of Domestic Fowl (*Gallus domesticus*) Produced in Asaba Delta State Nigeria

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Abstract

*Poultry farming is facing a lot of difficulties presently in the country mainly due to high cost of feeds and other factors. This study set out to establish the effects of orange fleshed sweet potato(OFSP)- meal on the growth and carcass weight of Domestic Fowl (*Gallus domesticus*) produced in Asaba –Delta State, Nigeria. The study was an experimental study of two groups: Experimental group and control group for ten weeks. At the beginning of the experiment, the whole birds (100 birds) were fed with broiler starter mash until the fourth week when they were divided into two groups: Group A (the experimental Group of 50 birds) and the Group B (the control Group of 50 birds), after which their weights were taken. Ten (10) birds were randomly picked from each group and their weights recorded. From the 5th week to the 10th week the birds in Group A were fed with OFSP-meal to 70% broiler finisher. Group B birds were fed with normal broiler finisher and at the end of the 10th week, the weights recorded. From the 5th week to the 10th week, the birds in Group A were fed with OFSP-meal mixed with broiler finisher compounded to the ratio of 3:7, that is, 30% OFSP-meal to 70% broiler finisher. Group B birds were fed with normal broiler finisher at the end of the 10th week, the weights and carcass weights of the birds were taken. The results shewed that the mean weights of the birds in the experimental group (3.85kg) compared favorably with the average generally accepted weight of the bird's specie (Rhode Island Red) of 3.90kg. What this means is that OFSP-meal can be used as a source of non-cereal energy sources complement in poultry feeds. This is good news for poultry farmers. The study among others recommended that the Government should promulgate the sweet potato –flour policy requiring feed millers to incorporate OFSP-meal/flour in their feed formulation.*

Introduction

Nigeria's poultry industry worth £4.2 billion according to the United Nations Food and Agricultural Organization (UNFAO) is a major protein source for over 200 million people. But the sector, which contributes 9% - 10% to the GDP, has struggled in the last three years and many operators have abandoned their businesses due to high costs of the constantly rising ingredients for the feed (Akanbi,2023).

It is certainly not the best of times for poultry farmers in Nigeria as they continue to battle the problems of unabated rise in the cost of production and the fall in the purchasing power of the people. The rising cost of production naturally translates to a higher cost of chicken and eggs, making it very expensive for the consumers, thereby worsening the protein malnutrition problem in the country.

Protein malnutrition and what the World Health Organization (WHO) called Hidden Hunger is real in the country, especially with the rising food prices and insecurity. According to the 2021 Global Hunger Index, Nigeria is ranked 98th out of 107 countries among the 10 hungriest countries in the world which include countries like Afghanistan, Haiti and Chad. Nigeria also performs poorly on the Global Hidden Hunger Index- the measure of essential minerals and vitamins in food. These micro-nutrients deficiencies account for approximately 7% of the global disease burden (Obike, 2021). This contributes to low human functionality and poor work productivity. The level of animal protein intake (a few grammes per capita per day) represents about one tenth of the level of intake in some advanced countries. Poultry keeping provides a method by which rapid transformation in animal protein consumption can be achieved in the country. However, this can take place only after the productive process has been modernized and modified.

Poultry keeping in the country (particularly the keeping of domestic fowl) generally follow traditional lines without the innovations which modern scientific endeavors have introduced; thus the birds under this system are characterized by slow rate of growth, low productivity with low feed efficiency and heavy parasitic and disease infection (Oluyemi and Roberts, 1999). In some commercial poultry farms, the cost of production, especially cost of feeds is making poultry farmers produce at maginal profit at best and at worst case scenario.

The energy in poultry diet is derived mainly from cereals. Those available in the country includes maize, millet, sorghum, rice and to some extent wheat. Non-cereals carbohydrate includes cassava which can be used for up to 50%-60% of the growers and layers diets without detrimental effects on the performance

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of the birds (Oluyemi and Roberts, 1999). Recent studies indicate that sweet potatoes and cassava have better metabolisable energy value than cocoyam and yam when these are included in chick's diets.

Statement of the Problem

Poultry feeds must contain above all energy feeds. The energy in poultry feeds is derived mainly from cereals. The cereals for feed formulation are maize, millet, sorghum (guinea corn), rice and to some extent wheat. The main cereals for feed production in Nigeria is maize. The price of maize is raising almost on a daily basis presently because of several factors as worsening conflict between farmers and herders in the middle belt states of Adamawa, Benue, Kaduna Nasarawa, Plateau and Taraba; The decade long Boko Haram insurgency in the north; banditry, kidnapping for ransom in the whole country; Ukraine/Russia war; a weakening naira and high fuel prices.

According to Akanbi (2023), some operators in the industry disclosed that the high cost of raw materials: maize, soya beans and others which constitute about 70 percent of the raw materials for poultry feeds have had their prices above normal. Due to these problems, local output has trailed consumption for years, sparking importation and having dire consequences for the naira and job creation (Jimoh, 2022).

Non-cereal carbohydrates like cassava, sweet potatoes can be used in place of maize in the production of poultry feeds. But the problem is that these non-cereal carbohydrates have limitations in that they need some processing before use and have low protein content, hence the need for this study to find out the effects of Orange Fleshed Sweet Potato (OFSP)-meal on the Growth and carcass Weight of Domestic Fowl.

Purpose of the Study

The goal of this study will be to ascertain the effects of using Orange Flesh Sweet Potato (OFSP)-meal on growth and carcass weight of Domestic Fowl production in Asaba, Delta State.

The specific objectives will be to determine:

1. The growth and development rate (weight) of Domestic Fowls feed with OFSP-meal.
2. The carcass weight of the birds at the end of 10weeks.

Review of Related Literature

Orange Fleshed Sweet Potato (OFSP) was introduced into the country in 2015. It was meant to boost the nutritional status of children and also help reduce the country's import of wheat and maize drastically.

The potato was developed by the International Potato Centre abbreviated by Spanish acronym (CIP) and Partners. The Partners in Africa-Empowering Novel, Agric-Business Led Employment, technologies African Agricultural Transformation (ENABLE TAAT) in conjunction with the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) Ibadan developed two varieties-king J and Mothers Delight, which are different from Irish potato.

According to Adedamola (2018), they contain a lot of water, vitamin A, high carotene and low level of sugar. Akinferiwa (2022) reported that the variety is good for fish and poultry feed production. OFSP is a good source of non-digestible dietary fibre, specific minerals, different vitamins and antioxidants. So poultry can consume OFSP as the staple crop because of high concentration of carbohydrates. Again Sweet potato generally provides more edible energy per hectare than wheat, rice, maize or cassava. It is also a good source of dietary fibre (2.5g-3.3g/100g), potassium, vitamins C and E, and has a low glycemic index (Alawode, 2017).

The United States Department of Agriculture-USDA (2018), describing the proximate composition of OFSP stated that its protein is similar to those of potato (2%), higher than that of cassava (1.4%), yam (1.5%), but lower than maize (9.4%), rice (7.1%), wheat (12.6%), sorghum (11.6%).

OFSP has high starch, (64.41%) concentration higher than the staple cereal, roots and tubers. Starch is an important energy sources for poultry. So poultry can consume OFSP as the staple crop because of high concentration of carbohydrates.

Research methodology

The design of the study was quasi-experimental. It was a pretest posttest non-randomised control group design.

Materials:

(1) Chicks: A total of one hundred (100) day – old chicks of Rhode Island Red (RIR) breed was used. RIR breed is bred for the table birds (for meat) as they produce a good carcass. They are easy to manage, very hardly and docile.

(2) Feeds: Compounded broiler starter and broiler finisher mash were purchased from a renowned store.

(3) Orange Fleshed Sweet Potato (OFSP)-Meal: Fresh bags of OFSP were purchased from Benue state where the potatoes were widely grown. The potatoes were thoroughly washed, shred and air dried and then ground into powder/meal.

(4) Specialized Treatment/Vaccination Schedule for the Vaccination

Age (in weeks)	Operations
0	Intraocular Vaccination.
2	Fowl Pox Vaccination.
6	Vaccination against fowl typhoid and New castle disease.
7	Deworming.

NB: Tylo-Dox Extra WSP was administered via drinking water for five days to prevent gastro-intestinal tract and respiratory infections at 4th week.

Rearing: The birds were taken to the brooder pen after purchase from the farm. The brooder pen had hovers and heat supplied by electric bulbs. The birds were here for 4 weeks (28 days). After 4weeks of age, the birds were transferred from the brooder to the rearing units. It was at this stage that the birds were randomly divided into two groups of fifty (50) birds each as follows:

GROUP A (Experimental Group) 50 birds

and

GROUP B (Control Group) 50 birds

NB: The rearing system is intensive (Deep Litter) system.

NB: The birds were all fed with broiler starter mash until the point of separation at 4weeks (28 days).

At this stage (group stage) a random sample of the weights of the birds were taken. Ten (10) of the birds were randomly picked from each group and their weights recorded thus:

Table1: Initial Life Weight (Weight in Kg)

S/NO	GROUP A	GROUP B
1	1.8	1.8
2	1.6	1.7
3	1.6	1.8
4	1.6	1.7
5	1.7	1.4
6	1.8	1.7
7	1.7	1.7
8	1.8	1.7
9	1.7	1.8
10	1.7	1.6
TOTAL	17.0	16.9
MEAN	1.70 Kg	1.69 Kg

Research Condition Treatment means that the birds in this group (GROUP A) were fed with OFSP meal mixed with broiler finisher mash to the ratio of 3:7 that is 30% OFSP mixed with 70% broiler finisher mash from 5 weeks -10 weeks.

Control means that the birds in this group (GROUP B) were fed with normal broiler finisher mash from 5 weeks -10 weeks.

Result:

At the end of the 10th week, the weights of the birds were taken to see how far the treatment group faired with the consumption of OFSP – meal mixed with broiler finisher mash, whether they were able to grow and convert the feed to adequate meat production (weight gain).

For the result, ten (10) birds were again randomly picked from each group and the weights recorded thus:

Table 2: Final Life Weight (Wt in kg)

S/NO	GROUP A	GROUP B
1	4.2	4.5
2	4.8	3.8
3	3.8	4.0
4	3.4	3.8
5	3.6	4.8
6	3.4	5.4
7	3.0	3.4
8	4.2	3.8
9	3.8	4.2
10	4.3	3.4
TOTAL	38.5	41.1
MEAN	3.85 Kg	4.11 Kg

Discussion / Interpretation:

The weight of the birds as indicated in the table 2 above showed that the weights of the birds fed with OFSP meal are not much different from the ones fed with normal broiler finisher mash.

It could also be seen that the average / mean weight of the birds in group A (3.85 kg) compared favourably well with the recognized average weight (3.90kg) of Rhode Island Red (RIR) birds generally. According to Komolafe, Adegbola, Are and Ashaye (1980), the average weight of (RIR)bird is 3.9 kg for the cock.

The result is in consonance with the view of Akinfenwa (2022) that the OFSP variety is good for fish and poultry feeds production. To him, poultry can consume OFSP as the staple crop because of high concentration of carbohydrates (64.41%). This is a welcome news to poultry farmers who are presently grappling with high cost of poultry feeds as a result of high cost of maize which is presently being sold at the cost of fifty-five thousand Naira (₦ 55,000) for a bag as against the OFSP being sold at the cost of eighteen thousand Naira (₦18,000) for a bag (Onitsha Relief Market Price as at 09/08/23).

Table 3: Summary of the mean carcass weight of the birds

GROUPS	Mean Carcass Weight
EXEPEREMENTAL/GROUP A	2.70Kg
CONTROL/GROUP B	2.88Kg

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The mean carcass weights of the birds also compared well with carcass weight of well-fed birds. According to Oluyemi and Roberts (1999), the carcass weight is about 65%-70% of the live weight of the birds, and that was the reflected above.

NB: The giblets which consist of the heart, gizzard and liver were included as part of the carcass.

Conclusion

OFSP – meal have positive effects on the growth and carcass weight of Domestic Fowl (*Gallus domesticus*) produced in Asaba-Delta State, Nigeria. OFSP - meal can be used as a complement in compounding poultry feeds in Nigeria.

Recommendations:

In the light of the result of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Poultry feed producers should incorporate OFSP in the compounding of their feeds especially broiler finishers.
2. Poultry farmers can try compounding/making their own feeds using different percentages/ ratio of OFSP: to maize in order to save cost and maximize their production.
3. Government should offer lifeline to poultry farmers who are being forced out of business because of high cost of production. They should look out for the real farmers and give them bail out, so that they can continue to stay in business.
4. Government should also come out with potato- policy, just like the cassava- policy in bread making. They should encourage poultry feed makers to incorporate OFSP – meal in their feeds.

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